

ISic4166

I.Sicily inscription 4166

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

volcanic

Object

stele

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lipara

Place of origin (modern)

Lipari

Provenance

Exact provenance unknown; seen by Libertini 'nel giardino Cappa sotto le mura del Castello donde precipito'

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description**Dimensions**

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout**Execution**

Engraved

Letter Forms**Letter heights:**

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI334715

1. Νικο[β]ούλας.

2.

Apparatus**Translation****Commentary****Digital identifiers:**

PHI 334715

Bibliography

Bernabò Brea, L., Cavalier, M., Campagna, L. 2003. Meligunìs Lipára. XII. Le iscrizioni lapidarie greche e latine delle isole eolie. Palermo. At 611

Libertini, G 1921. Le isole eolie nell'antichità greca e romana. Ricerche storiche ed archeologiche. Florence. At 227 no.60
undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.
Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 82

Licensed under a Creative
Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic4166. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4389977>